

SURVEY ON DEFINING PRACTICES IN ONTOLOGIES

– Report –

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In preparation of the
International Workshop On Definitions In Ontologies (DO 2013)
held in conjunction with the
4th International Conference on Biomedical Ontology (ICBO 2013)

Concordia University
Montreal, Quebec, Canada

July, 2013

SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

University at Buffalo
The State University of New York

Survey on Defining Practices in Ontologies

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This document reports the results of a survey on defining practices in ontologies conducted in preparation of the International Workshop on Definitions in Ontologies (DO 2013) held on July 7, 2013, in Montreal, in conjunction with the Fourth International Conference on Biomedical Ontologies 2013 (ICBO2013), itself part of the Semantic Trilogy '13 event.

1. Background

Ontologies built using OBO Foundry principles are advised to include both formal (logical) definitions and natural language definitions. Depending on the effort, one or the other can be underrepresented. Possible explanations to this bottleneck are the high cost of producing well-written definitions; an insufficient understanding of the nature of natural language definitions or of logic; the lack of an operational theory of definitions; the lack of studies that evaluate usability and effectiveness of definitions in ontologies; a paucity of tools to help with definition authoring and checking.

Producing natural language definitions is time-consuming, costly and prone to all kinds of inconsistencies. Producing logical definitions that are effective, correct, and communicative is also difficult. It is therefore worth exploring different ways of assisting, with automation, creation and quality control of definitions.

Accordingly, we thought it would be useful to gather interested researchers and developers to reflect upon general themes as the selection and modeling of defining information; the relation between definitions in specific domains as opposed to domain-independent definitions; the theoretical underpinnings of definitions; tools that can facilitate relating logical and natural language definitions. In addition, we wanted to encourage participation by different communities using definitions so that their needs can be exposed.

To address these issues, we organized a half-day workshop aimed at discussing questions, ideas and existing projects regarding definitions in ontologies. The expected outcomes of the workshop were to get an overall view of the needs of the users so as to best orient research on the definition authoring side, as well as to get a diagnosis of the difficulties faced by the latter in order to guide groundwork on definitions and their production.

We present here the results of the survey on defining practices that was conducted in preparation of the general discussion at the workshop.

2. Objectives

The objective was to gather information on the practices and needs of the ontology community with respect to definitions – logical and textual – in order to guide the discussion session aimed at creating a prioritized list of needs and best practices in definitions. We invited the ontology community to give us feedback on their experience by filling in a questionnaire published on the Internet. The web-based survey was sent to several ontology lists; 14 people responded to the questionnaire. The small number of participants does not allow us to draw statistically

significant conclusions; their answers are nevertheless indicative of the practices and needs related to definitions in ontologies.

3. Methodology

The 15 questions – some of which include sub-questions – of the questionnaire can be grouped into three larger categories:

- **User-oriented questions:** types of users; their role in the ontology project on which they are working; their use of logical and/or textual definitions; their training in logical and/or textual definition authoring; the kind of assistance needed with respect to definitions in ontologies. [Q: 1, 2, 8a, 9a-d, 10a-b, 11a-b, 14]
- **Ontology-oriented questions:** inclusion of logical and/or textual definitions in the ontologies. [Q: 3, 4a-c, 5a-b]
- **Definition-oriented questions:** usefulness of logical and textual definitions; major problems in definitions; desired enhancements to textual definitions. [Q: 6, 7, 8b, 12, 13]

Several types of questions were asked: closed yes/no questions; multiple choice questions with single or multiple answers, and open-ended textual (qualitative) questions.

Before a detailed analysis of the results of the questionnaire, we present a summary of the main results of this survey.

4. Summary of the results

4.1. Users and their needs

4.1.1. Respondents' profile (Q1-2)

Most of the respondents work as ontologists regardless of their primary profession. They are thus more likely to be involved in definition authoring and to express needs related to these activities, which is confirmed by the results to the other questions in this section.

4.1.2. Use of definitions (Q8a-b)

The majority of the respondents report using – consulting or writing – definitions ‘often’, which is indicative of the fact that definitions are central to the ontology work.

Two types of uses seem to emerge: mostly internal uses related to the activity of ontology development, and, to a lesser extent, external uses related to the application of ontologies.

The answers suggest that respondents are primarily concerned with logical definitions. The lesser use of textual definitions may be due to their lacking quality. These results suggest, in turn, that the roles of the term, the logical definition and the textual one in ontologies could be more precisely defined.

4.1.3. Definition consultation (Q9a-d)

All of the respondents report using logical and/or textual definitions to get a clear understanding of the terms in the ontologies; moreover, the majority of them report using definitions ‘often’ rather than ‘sometimes’.

The use of logical definitions is quantitatively closer to ‘very often’ than to ‘rarely’ (7/12 vs. 5/12 respondents). However, the use of textual definitions is even more frequent than that of logical definitions.

The frequent use of both logical and textual definitions seems to indicate that they play an important role in the proper understanding of what is represented in the ontologies.

4.1.4. Definition writing (Q10a-b)

The majority of the respondents report engaging in definition authoring activities.

The defining activity is not only limited to definition creation, generally, from texts and consultation of experts; it also includes definition revision and ‘translation’ of textual definitions to/from logical ones.

As for the defining form, the classical definition structure – genus + differentia – is the preferred one.

4.1.5. Training in definition writing (Q11a-b)

Half of the respondents have had no training in definition writing. Among the other half of the respondents, most have had training in both logical and textual definition writing, and one only in logical definition writing. In only a few cases the training in definition writing was ontology-oriented. It would thus be interesting to create this kind of specific training.

4.1.6. Users’ needs (Q14)

The ontology community would mostly welcome general principles for definition writing. Half of the respondents were also interested in ontology-specific training for writing logical definitions. The results also suggest that training and tools related to textual definitions tend to be considered as nice-to-have but not as important as assistance with logical definitions.

4.2. Ontologies and Definitions

4.2.1. Kinds of ontologies (Q3)

Most of the respondents work on ontologies related to the biomedical domain, two work on an upper level ontology, the Basic Formal Ontology. The other ontologies cover varied areas.

4.2.2. Importance of definitions in ontologies

4.2.2.1. Importance of logical definitions (Q4a-c)

The majority of the ontologies on which the respondents answered these questions include logical definitions. However, in most of the ontologies, less than half of the entities are logically defined; only in one are 75-100% of the entities defined.

These results suggest to us that more logical definitions will be added in the future, in particular if the ontology developers want to comply with the OBO Foundry principles. Hence, authoring tools that allow for the semi-automatic creation of logical definitions would probably be helpful.

4.2.2.2. Importance of textual definitions (Q5a-b)

All the ontologies on which the respondents answered these questions except one have textual definitions. Moreover, by contrast with logical definitions, the textual definitions are well represented: in 10/12 ontologies, more than half of the entities are defined with a textual definition; the coverage rate in 2/3 of all the ontologies is even comprised between 75% and 100% of the entities.

These results tend to indicate that the needs related to textual definitions may be less pronounced than those related to logical definitions.

4.3. Definitions in Ontologies

4.3.1. Usefulness of definitions (Q6-7)

Both logical and textual definitions are subjectively considered by the respondents as extremely important in ontologies.

4.3.2. Problems with definitions (Q12)

Four large types of problems were mentioned by the respondents. These are related to:

1. the information content of textual definitions
 - insufficiently informative
 - too informative/too complex
 - outdated
 - absence of standard defining patterns
2. logical issues
 - vague
 - circular
 - self-contradictory
3. the writing and style of the definitions
 - poorly written
 - inconsistent in style
4. coverage
 - multiple definitions
 - absence of definitions

4.3.3. Desired enhancements in textual definitions (Q13)

The most frequently mentioned desired enhancements to textual definitions relate (i) to their authoring methods – the creation of definition templates –, and (ii) to their content and form – an increase in the readability of the definitions. The latter enhancement includes not only stylistic matters, but also adaptability of the defining vocabulary to different types of users, which is also related to the adaptability of the defining content. Current user-oriented trends of research in terminology and lexicography could be helpful in this respect.

Among the other mentioned enhancements, we note the development of tools or methods to convert textual definitions to/from logical ones, issues that have started to be explored in the ontology community. Finally, the inclusion of examples is also mentioned, although this enhancement is not as such related to definitions; it may however be indicative of definitions

that are not explicit and content-wise not rich enough to be useful to the users – although in some (or maybe many) cases it might not be related to the lacking of definitions at all, only to the fact that examples tend to fulfill a different cognitive need.

4.3.4. Further comments and suggestions (Q15)

Tools should be developed to help ontology developers implement general principles on definitions.

5. Detailed analysis of the results

The following sections report the details of the responses to the questionnaire. The questions are grouped thematically, according to the three categories presented in section 3.

5.1. Users and their needs

This section reports the results relative to the users and their needs regarding definitions in ontologies. It comprises six subsections corresponding to the profiles of the respondents; to their use of definitions; to their perceived usefulness of definitions in ontologies; to their definition writing activities and training; and to their needs with respect to definitions in ontologies.

5.1.1. Respondents' profile

The first two questions were related to the primary profession and role of the respondents in the ontology project on which they are working. They were intended to get an idea of 'who works as what' in the ontology projects, and 'what is the background of the people involved in the different roles playing a part in ontology development'.

Q1. What is your profession?

This question was an open-ended question to which the respondents could answer freely. This resulted in three of the respondent including more than one profession, and one listing the types of professions involved in their ontology project. To determine the latter one's profession, we considered that respondent's answer to the second question (Q2). The 18 listed professions can be categorized into five larger types, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Respondents' profession

It is interesting to note that one of the three respondents who consider their primary profession as ‘ontologist’ has no other profession listed; the two other ones also list ‘philosopher’, and one further includes ‘researcher’. The ‘other’ category includes ‘economist’.

Q2. What is your role in the ontology project on which you are working?

This question was a multiple-choice question for which several answers could apply. Five participants gave multiple answers. As can be seen in Figure 2, most of the 22 reported roles correspond to ‘ontologist’ and ‘computer scientist’. The detailed figures show that half of the respondents working as computer scientists (4/8) also work as ontologists. Interestingly, among the 10 respondents to report having the role of ontologist, only two work as domain experts – the third one also works as a computer scientist. This suggests that the respondents work closely with the contents of the ontology and probably also with definitions, which seems to be confirmed by the rest of the survey.

Figure 2: Respondents' role in ontology project

Cross-analyses of this data allow getting a clearer view on:

- the type of work carried out by different professions in the ontology projects (see Figure 3);

Figure 3: Roles per profession

- the background training of the different roles involved in ontology development (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Professions per role in ontology

According to the results in Figure 3, most of the professions involved in ontology development are mainly working as ontologists. Unsurprisingly, the respondents who reported having the profession of ontologist did not list any other role in the ontology project (although two out of three also listed other professions). The notable exceptions are computer scientists who are mostly involved in computing tasks.

Figure 4 shows that whether the respondents work as ontologists, computer scientists, or domain experts, their background is somewhat varied. The most relevant result for our study is however that people working as ontologists have the most diverse background – although, we don't know what is the actual training of the three respondents whose profession is 'ontologist'. We presume, indeed, that ontologists are those who are the most likely to work with definitions. As they have quite different backgrounds that do not, in principle, involve training in definition authoring, we can expect them to have certain needs regarding definitions, which is confirmed by the results to the other questions in this section.

5.1.2. Use of definitions

The following question is meant to get an idea of the degree to which people working on ontologies use (consult or write) logical and/or textual definitions – for a more detailed report on the use, see questions Q9a-d on consultation (section 5.1.3) and Q10a-b on authoring (section 5.1.4).

Q8a. Do you use logical and/or textual definitions in your work?

The results to this mandatory multiple-choice question show that a large majority (12/14) of the respondents report using definitions 'often'; the rest (2/14) report using them 'sometimes' (see Figure 5). Interestingly, no one declared they 'never' used definitions. Although not statistically significant, this result is indicative of the fact that definitions are central to the ontology work¹.

Figure 5: Frequency of use of definitions

To better understand the use made of logical and textual definitions, we completed this question with an open-ended optional one. All of the respondents answered this question.

¹ The importance of definitions is also suggested by the large number of slides on definitions at a recent ontology meeting held in Buffalo, NY.

Q8b. Please explain why not or what is your use of logical and/or textual definitions.

We summarize hereafter the main uses of definitions in ontologies. In most cases, the respondents did not specify whether they were considering logical or textual definitions, but the answers often suggest the use of logical definitions.

- clarifying differences between classes
- consistency checking
- ontology/data mapping
- building taxonomies
- query answering
- annotation

Two types of uses seem to emerge: mostly internal uses related to the activity of ontology development, and, to a lesser extent, external uses related to the application of ontologies. This suggests that definitions are used for a wide variety of tasks and supports the idea that ontologies should aim at including definitions for all its entities, as it is stated in the OBO Foundry principles.

In addition, two respondents commented on why textual definitions are sometimes less used: because they are redundant with the term – "often in the case of defined classes" –; and because they come as a last resort after the term and the logical definition – "users look first at the label (and usually stop there), second at the logical axioms, and only third at the textual definition". These answers suggest that the quality of textual definitions might not always meet the users' expectations and that the roles of the term, the logical definition and the textual one in ontologies could be more precisely defined.

5.1.3. Definition consultation

The following series of questions (Q9a-d) is intended to see to what extent the respondents consult definitions and, if they don't, why. These questions also give an idea of the usefulness of the logical and/or textual definitions to ontology users².

Q9a. Do you use the logical and/or textual definition of a term to get a clear understanding of the term?

The results to this mandatory multiple-choice question show that all of the respondents report using logical and/or textual definitions to get a clear understanding of the terms in the ontologies (Q9a); moreover, the majority of them report using definitions 'often' rather than 'sometimes' (see Figure 6).

² A more detailed account on the usefulness of definitions in ontologies can be found below, in section 5.3.1.

Figure 6: Use of definitions to understand terms

To get a more precise picture of the consultation of logical and textual definitions, respondents were further asked to rate their frequency of use of both types of definitions separately on a five-point scale ranging from 'rarely' (1) to 'very often' (5) (Q9b-c). As these questions were optional, the total number of respondents varies from question to question.

Q9b. If your answer is 'sometimes' or 'often', on any day when you work on the ontology, how often do you consult the logical definitions?

The results to this mandatory multiple-choice question show that the reported use of logical definitions is quantitatively closer to 'very often' (7/12 respondents answered 4 and 5) than to 'rarely' (5/12 respondents answered 1 and 2), as can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Consultation frequency of logical definitions

Q9c. If your answer is 'sometimes' or 'often', on any day when you work on the ontology, how often do you consult the textual definitions?

However, the results in Figure 8 show that the reported use of textual definitions is even more frequent than that of logical definitions. Here, the frequency ratings ranging from 3 to 5 ('very often') add up to 9/11 respondents – in contrast to 2 respondents who answered 'rarely'.

Figure 8: Consultation frequency of textual definitions

The last optional open-ended question of the series (Q9d) was intended to see, if applicable, why users wouldn't use definitions.

Q9d. If your answer is 'never', please explain why.

As all the respondents report using definitions at least 'sometimes', this question appeared superfluous in the present case. One person did however explain that definitions are important whenever he/she needs to use them, but that ontology work involves many other tasks, such as maintenance, that do not require to pay attention to definitions.

To summarize, these results suggest that definitions, both logical and textual, are useful to ontology users – at least to ontology developers, as the results to questions Q10a-b might suggest. Their frequent use seems to indicate that definitions play an important role in the proper understanding of what is represented in the ontologies. Therefore, for an ontology to be successfully used, definitions should not be neglected in it.

5.1.4. Definition writing

In order to better understand the respondents' interaction with definitions in ontologies, we asked them if they were involved in the writing of logical and/or textual definitions for the ontology or for the ontology's specifications, and, if applicable, to provide some explanations regarding this activity (Q10a-b).

Q10a. Do you write logical and/or textual definitions for the ontology or for its specifications?

The results to the first mandatory closed question show – see Figure 9 – that about half of the respondents report writing both logical and textual definitions (8/14), the rest of the respondents are dispersed in 3 groups: 3 report writing logical definitions, 2 textual ones, and 1 is not engaged in definition writing. Overall, the vast majority of the respondents report engaging in definition authoring activities – which might also explain the importance given to definitions in the previous series of questions (Q9a-d).

Figure 9: Definition writing in ontologies

The next question was intended to get a more precise idea of the respondents' definition authoring activity.

Q10b. If your answer is 'yes', please provide some specifications regarding this activity.

This optional open-ended question was answered by 9/14 respondents, but only 7 answers were relevant – one of the answers that was discarded read that the respondent didn't understand part of the question, and the other one was not related to definitions.

To summarize the responses, the defining activity is not only limited to definition creation, generally, from texts and consultation of experts; it also includes definition revision and 'translation' of textual definitions to/from logical ones. Some respondents provided information on the definition writing methodology: it seems that the ontology projects in which they are involved do not provide precise specifications on how to write definitions. However, the classical definition structure – genus + differentia – seems to be the preferred form.

5.1.5. Training in definition writing

To further understand the needs of the ontology community regarding definitions, we asked two questions related to the type of training, if any, that the respondents have had in writing logical and/or textual definitions (Q11a-b).

Q11a. Have you received any training in writing logical and/or textual definitions?

The first question was a mandatory multiple-choice question with a single answer. As it can be seen from Figure 10, half of the respondents (7/14) report having had no training in definition writing. This suggests that what would be mostly needed is training for that activity, which could be backed up with the creation of definition authoring tools. Among the other half of the respondents, 6 persons report having had training in both logical and textual definition writing, one reports having been trained only in logical definition writing, and no one only in textual definition writing.

Figure 10: Training in definition writing

This question was completed with an optional open-ended question aimed at seeing, if applicable, what kind of training the respondents had received.

Q11b. If your answer is 'yes', please specify.

6/7 respondents who reported having had some training in definition writing answered this question. We summarize the five kinds of approaches that were reported:

- logic courses
- training in general or ontology-specific definition standards
- reading best practices
- consulting with other ontologists
- using ontology development tools to creating logical definitions

Considering the answers, it seems that in only a few cases the training in definition writing was ontology-oriented. It would thus be interesting to create this kind of specific training.

5.1.6. Users' needs

The last user-oriented question relates to the kind of assistance that the respondents would see fit to enhance their experience with definitions in ontologies.

Q14. What kind of assistance would be useful for you to enhance your experience with definitions in ontologies?

This mandatory multiple-choice question included 7 suggestions and a box labeled 'other' in which the respondents could add further suggestions. The types of assistance deemed useful with respect to definitions in ontologies and their popularity are reported in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11: Users' needs

The results show that the ontology community would mostly welcome general principles for definition writing – the interest for these principles comes equally from respondents who haven't had training in definition writing as well as from those who have. One of the answers to question Q15 – section 5.4 below – however points out that tools should be developed to help ontology developers implement general principles on definitions.

Half of the respondents were also interested in ontology-specific training for writing logical definitions.

The usefulness of a definition-writing manual and of definition authoring tools is, in our view, surprisingly low, as these aids would probably be more suited than general principles to producing quality definitions – obviously a good manual or tool would integrate the general principles.

The results also suggest that training and tools related to textual definitions tend to be considered as nice-to-have but not as important as assistance with logical definitions. This result is in line with the profile of the respondents, as most of them seem to be actively involved in ontology development. It would, however, be interesting to complete this survey with one specifically directed, for example, to the domain experts who use the ontologies to see which type of definition – logical or textual – they mostly use.

Two respondents suggested further solutions to assist with definitions in ontologies: evaluation, and "reasons behind such principles and behind each definition method". The latter explanatory information would be something to include in a definition-writing manual; the former aspect could also be addressed in a manual and, in addition, implemented in a definition checking/evaluation tool.

5.2. Ontologies and definitions

This section reports the results relative to the ontologies with which the respondents are primarily involved and the extent to which these include definitions. It comprises two main subsections corresponding to the kinds of domains covered by the ontologies, and to the importance of definitions in ontologies. The latter is further subdivided into results on the importance of logical definitions and of textual definitions.

5.2.1. Kinds of ontologies

The following mandatory open-ended question was included to have a picture of the kind of ontologies on which the respondents work.

Q3. With which ontology do you primarily work?

The respondents were expected to state the ontology with which they primarily work. However, half of them reported working (primarily) on more than one. The total number of ontologies therefore adds up to 18 for 14 respondents. Most of the respondents work on ontologies related to the biomedical domain; two work on an upper level ontology, the Basic Formal Ontology. The other ontologies cover varied areas.

5.2.2. Importance of definitions in ontologies

To assess the importance of definitions in ontologies, we further asked a series of questions relating to the presence of both logical (Q4a-c) and textual (Q5a-b) definitions in them. It must be noted that these results are not representative of all the ontologies mentioned by the respondents, as some of them stated more than one ontology. We will however consider that the answers relate in each case to a single ontology – although we won't consider which one.

5.2.2.1. Importance of logical definitions

Q4a. Does the ontology contain logical definitions?

The results to this first mandatory closed question show that the majority of the ontologies that the respondents had in mind when answering this question include logical definitions (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Ontologies with logical definitions

This optimistic result must however be relativized by the results of the following related

question. This optional multiple-choice question was, indeed, intended to see to what extent the entities in the ontologies are logically defined.

Q4c. If your answer is 'yes', what percentage of the terms in the ontology have logical definitions associated with them?

Among the 12 respondents who answered positively to the previous question (Q4a), only 11 reported the proportion of defined entities in the ontologies they had in mind (see Figure 13). It is interesting to see that, in most of the ontologies (7/11), less than half of the entities are logically defined, and that only one ontology has logical definitions for between 75% and 100% of the entities.

Figure 13: Percentage of logical definitions

As logical definitions are one of the main features that make ontologies useful, it is surprising that they are not as frequent as one would expect. It would be interesting to inquire further into the reasons of such a small coverage in logical definitions. The results on the users' needs reported in section 5.1.6 may explain it in part, as many of the respondents seem interested in training courses for writing logical definitions. The reason would therefore be a lack of proper training. In any case, these results suggest to us that more logical definitions will be added in the future, in particular if ontology developers want to comply with the OBO Foundry principles. Hence, authoring tools that allow for the semi-automatic creation of logical definitions would probably be helpful.

To get an idea of the kind of logical definitions included in ontologies, we asked the following optional question.

Q4b. If your answer is 'yes', please give an example of logical definition.

Only 7 respondents gave examples of logical definitions. From inspection, we recognize that 4 of the logical definitions are in an OWL syntax and, the rest, in various different syntaxes.

5.2.2.2. Importance of textual definitions

The same quantitative questions were asked for textual definitions.

Q5a. Does the ontology contain textual definitions?

The results show that all the ontologies that the respondents had in mind when answering this question except one have textual definitions, as can be seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Ontologies with textual definitions

Moreover, by contrast with logical definitions, the textual definitions are well represented, as can be seen from the results of the next question.

Q5b. If your answer is 'yes', what percentage of the terms in the ontology have textual definitions associated with them?

Here too, one of the respondents who answered positively to the previous question (Q5a) failed to report the percentage of textual definitions included in the ontology. Nonetheless, the overall coverage for textual definitions is high, as shown in Figure 15: in 10/12 ontologies, more than half of the entities are defined with a textual definition. Surprisingly, the coverage rate in 2/3 of all the ontologies is even comprised between 75% and 100% of the entities.

Figure 15: Percentage of textual definitions

These results tend to indicate that the needs related to textual definitions may be less pronounced than those related to logical definitions, as ontologies cover already rather well this aspect. Note however that, according to the results related to question Q8b on the uses of definitions – section 5.1.2 –, textual definitions seem less used than the mere term or the logical definitions, and that this could be due to some lacking in the textual definitions. It would

therefore be interesting to further analyze textual definitions to see if there is room for qualitative improvement.

5.3. Definitions in ontologies

This section reports the results on definitions in ontologies as such. It comprises three subsections. The first one is related to the usefulness of definitions in ontologies; the second one, to the kinds of problems found in textual definitions; and, the third one, to the kinds of enhancements that could be done with respect to textual definitions.

5.3.1. Usefulness of definitions

The first two definition-oriented questions (Q6-7) relate to the usefulness of definitions in ontologies as perceived by the respondents. Respondents were asked to rate the usefulness of both types of definitions separately on a five-point scale ranging from 'not useful' (1) to 'indispensable' (5).

Q6. How useful do you find logical definitions in an ontology?

To the first question on logical definitions, half of the respondents agree on their indispensability in ontologies (see Figure 16). However, by contrast with textual definitions, some respondents (3/14) consider logical definitions to be moderately or even not so useful.

Figure 16: Usefulness of logical definitions

Q7. How useful do you find textual definitions in an ontology?

To the second question on textual definitions, all the respondents find them at least moderately indispensable (see Figure 17). Overall, though, most of the respondents find them less indispensable than logical ones (8/14 scored textual definitions 4/5).

Figure 17: Usefulness of textual definitions

To summarize, it appears that both logical and textual definitions are subjectively considered by the respondents as extremely important in ontologies. These results suggest that definitions, whatever their form, are central to the proper understanding of the entities represented in ontologies and that this subject deserves proper attention.

5.3.2. Problems with definitions

The following mandatory open-ended question was meant to find out the major problems that the respondents have encountered with textual definitions. The responses to this question might also be useful to understanding why, according to some respondents, textual definitions are reported to be often the last element – after the term and the logical definition – to be consulted by ontology users.

Q12. What are the major problems that you have encountered when consulting textual definitions? (For example, when you consult a definition to get a clear understanding of a term in an ontology in order to apply it correctly to annotations.)

As shown in Figure 18, we summarized the responses given to this question in 10 categories, which can be grouped into four larger types of problems related to:

1. the information content of textual definitions
 - insufficiently informative
 - too informative/too complex
 - outdated
 - absence of standard defining patterns
2. logical issues
 - vague
 - circular
 - self-contradictory
3. the writing and style of the definitions
 - poorly written

- inconsistent in style
4. coverage
- multiple definitions
 - absence of definitions

Figure 18: Types of problems in textual definitions

The problems in categories 3 and 4 can be rather easily addressed with simple tools. These can check for the absence of definitions and the presence of more than one definition, as well as for spelling errors and the compliance to the language-specific style conventions for defining³ (see for example Köhler et al. 2006; Seppälä 2006). The problems in the other categories may also receive automated assistance, although this requires further research regarding those questions.

5.3.3. Desired enhancements in textual definitions

Another way to approach issues related to textual definitions was to ask the respondents to answer another mandatory open-ended question about the enhancements they would see fit for textual definitions.

Q13. What enhancements would you like to see in textual definitions in ontologies?

Here again, we summarized the answers by grouping them under six categories of desired enhancements, as shown in Figure 19.

³ Definition writing stylistic conventions vary from one language to another, and may even vary from one project or resource to another.

Figure 19: Desired enhancements in textual definitions

The results show that the most frequently mentioned desired enhancements to textual definitions relate (i) to their authoring methods – the creation of definition templates –, and (ii) to their content and form – an increase in the readability of the definitions. The latter enhancement includes not only stylistic matters, but also adaptability of the defining vocabulary to different types of users, which is also related to the adaptability of the defining content. Current user-oriented trends of research in terminology and lexicography could be helpful in this respect (Granger and Paquot 2012; León Araúz and San Martín 2012; San Martín and León Araúz 2013).

Among the other mentioned enhancements, we note the development of tools or methods to convert textual definitions to/from logical ones, issues that are started to be explored in the ontology community (see for example Rassinoux et al. 2007; Stevens et al. 2010; Stevens et al. 2011; Trombert-Paviot et al. 2003). Finally, the inclusion of examples is also mentioned, although this enhancement is not as such related to definitions; it may however be indicative of definitions that are not explicit and content-wise not rich enough to be useful to the users – although in some (or maybe many) cases it might not be related to the lacking of definitions at all, only to the fact that examples tend to fulfill a different cognitive need (Seppälä 2012, chapter 1, section 1.3).

5.4. Further comments and suggestions

To conclude the questionnaire, we asked a last optional open-ended question that allowed respondent to add any other suggestion on definitions in ontologies. This question was also aimed at receiving feedback on the contents of the survey.

Q15. Please let us know if you have any other comments or suggestions regarding definitions in ontologies or this questionnaire.

Six respondents added comments. Only three comments were usefully related to definitions in ontologies and mainly repeated what already appears in the results of the main part of the questionnaire. One respondent, however, brought up a new comment, which is that tools should be developed to help ontology developers implement general principles on definitions.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this survey on defining practices in ontologies suggests that definitions are central to ontologies, not only for computational reasons, but also for their proper development and use by humans.

Concerning users' needs, the survey results indicate that it would be valuable to establish ontology-oriented defining principles and manuals, backed up with tools to support ontology developers in implementing the recommendations. Moreover, specific ontology-oriented definition writing training courses or tutorials would also be among the priorities, in particular for logical definitions.

Finally, the current rather low definition coverage rate in ontologies suggests to us that, in light of the standards of good practice in ontology development, more logical, but also textual, definitions will (or, at least, should) be added in the future. Therefore, research efforts could be geared towards developing tools that allow for the (semi-)automatic creation of definitions, for example by generating textual definitions to/from logical ones.

Acknowledgements

Work on this survey was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the State University of New York at Buffalo.

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